

FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF INFLATION TARGETING IN RUSSIA

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Abstract: The article examines the specific features of the application of inflation targeting policy in the Russian Federation under conditions of economic instability, sanctions pressure, and external economic restrictions. The study analyzes the development of Russia's monetary policy from the mid-1990s to the present stage, including the transition to an inflation targeting regime in 2015. Particular attention is paid to the influence of inflation expectations, oil prices, exchange rates, money supply, and the level of public trust in state institutions on the effectiveness of the Central Bank's policy. The consequences of the global financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the sanctions imposed in 2022 for the Russian economy and the inflation targeting mechanism are also examined. Based on macroeconomic indicators, the study concludes that the effectiveness of inflation targeting in Russia largely depends on external economic factors, institutional stability, and public confidence in the state's monetary policy.

Keywords: inflation targeting, monetary policy, Central Bank of Russia, inflation, key interest rate, sanctions, exchange rate, inflation expectations, macroeconomic stability, Russian economy.

The monetary system of the Russian Federation developed gradually, passing through several stages of formation. Throughout this period, inflation remained one of the key objects of state regulation. In 1995, the Bank of Russia obtained a certain degree of independence from executive authorities in conducting monetary policy. As part of exchange rate stabilization measures, a currency corridor mechanism was introduced on July 8, 1995, replacing the previous managed floating exchange rate regime.

As a result of the Asian financial crisis, the sharp decline in global oil prices, and the difficult economic situation in the country, the government was forced to declare a default on its obligations in August 1998. The currency corridor was abolished, the national currency depreciated significantly, and galloping inflation was observed. The key objective for 1999 was the gradual reduction of inflation rates, as well as decreasing state intervention in market mechanisms of exchange rate formation in order to transition to a floating exchange rate regime in the future.

It is important to note that since the introduction of the new monetary policy reforms by the Central Bank and up to the present day, Russia and the Central Bank have not fully met all the requirements necessary for полноценное inflation targeting. As mentioned earlier, the effectiveness of inflation targeting largely depends on the independence of the Central Bank. A successful example of granting such independence can be seen in the United Kingdom's path toward an inflation targeting model suited to its national conditions. In the case of the Russian Federation, although the Bank of Russia possesses a degree of independence, certain key decisions regarding monetary policy reforms still remain under the control of the executive authorities.

In 2010, the Russian economy was overcoming the consequences of the global financial crisis of 2008. Compared to the period of 2007–2008, the Russian economy gradually began to recover. Due to energy exports and rising global energy prices, Russia managed to gradually emerge from the crisis and restore public confidence in the government and its economic policy.

However, inflation expectations and trust in the government changed significantly in 2014 amid the first wave of sanctions and the decline in global oil prices.

Thus, the main factors limiting the actions of the Russian government and the Central Bank are economic sanctions, declining energy prices, high inflation expectations, and reduced public confidence in the national currency. This was reflected in changes in the consumer price index during the period 2011–2014.

Figure 1. Consumer Price Index in the Russian Federation during 2011–2014 [1]

Next, let us examine the dynamics of the inflation rate in the Russian Federation during 2011–2014.

Inflation Rate in the Russian Federation during 2011–2014 [2]

Year	Inflation Rate (%)
2011	6,10
2012	6,58
2013	6,45
2014	11,36

During the period from 2011 to 2014, the inflation rate in Russia increased from 6.1% to 11.36%. In general, until 2014 the country maintained a relatively stable situation in the sphere of monetary policy.

Figure 2 illustrates the dynamics of oil prices from 2010 to 2015, demonstrating favorable conditions in the oil market for Russia during 2011–2014.

Figure 2. Dynamics of Oil Prices in Russia during 2010–2015 [2]

The reasons were the imposed sanctions, the decline in oil prices, and the depreciation of the ruble, which were reflected in increased inflationary pressure and a weakening of the government's reputation.

Analysis of Inflation Expectations and Public Trust in the Government in the Russian Federation during 2010–2025

Year	Inflation Expectations, %	Public Trust in the Government, %
2010	18,7	45
2011	16,5	47
2012	14,2	50
2013	12,8	52
2014	13,5	48
2015	16,4	46
2016	14,0	44
2017	12,0	42
2018	10,5	40
2019	9,0	38
2020	9,8	35
2021	13,0	33
2022	12,2	32
2023	14,2	30
2024	13,9	30
2025	13,7	28

It can be concluded that economic uncertainty in the country has increased business distrust toward the government.

Next, let us examine the indicators influencing inflation targeting.

Economic Indicators Influencing Inflation Targeting in the Russian Federation [3, 4]

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024

Annual Inflation (end of year)	4.9%	8.4%	11.9%	7.42%	9.52%
Oil Prices (Brent, USD/barrel)	41.69	70.89	100.94	82.5	81
Food Price Growth	6.7%	10.6 %	10.23%	8.86%	11.4%
Producer Price Index for Industrial Goods	5.1%	24.6 %	13.4%	-10.2%	4.5% (Q1–Q2)
Consumer Expectations Index	82%	78%	54%	65%	71% (Q1–Q2)
Money Supply Growth (M2)	14.3%	17.1 %	6.8%	25.4%	18.2% (Q1–Q2)
Central Bank Key Interest Rate (end of year)	4.25%	8.5%	7.5%	16%	21%

Next, let us examine the dynamics of macroeconomic indicators in Russia during the period from 2014 to 2024.

Macroeconomic Indicators in the Context of Inflation Targeting in Russia during 2014–2024 [5]

Year	Inflation (%)	Money Supply M2 (trillion rubles)	Nominal GDP (trillion rubles)	Monetization of the Economy (%)
2014	11,35	33,5	85	39,4
2015	12,91	34,5	83,2	41,5
2016	5,39	38	86	44,2
2017	2,51	42	92,1	45,6
2018	4,26	45	103,9	43,3
2019	3,04	50	110	45,5
2020	4,91	55	106,6	51,6
2021	8,39	60	130,8	45,9
2022	11,94	76,9	151,5	50,8
2023	7,42	92,5	171	54,1
2024	9,52	111	190	58,4

In 2015, Russia officially announced the transition to an inflation targeting regime. One of the key requirements of this approach was the termination of regular foreign exchange

interventions and the transition to indirect methods of influencing the ruble exchange rate. The main idea of the new policy was to maintain the required level of inflation in a controlled manner while ensuring its stability within established targets.

It was largely due to such policies, including the use of verbal intervention similar in some aspects to the policy implemented by the United States during the 2007–2008 financial crisis, that inflation decreased to a historic minimum of 4–5%. However, public trust in the government continued to decline due to socio-economic policies, such as the pension reform implemented in 2018, which further reduced income growth.

Significant changes also occurred during the pandemic period in 2020. Prices for essential goods began to rise, while economic processes slowed down and logistics chains were disrupted. These factors contributed to increased inflation expectations. At the same time, global prices for raw materials increased. Oil, gas, metals, and grain prices rose significantly during this period. As a resource-exporting country, Russia experienced rising prices in the domestic market. Fuel prices also increased, which affected logistics costs and consequently influenced subsequent economic processes.

The depreciation of the ruble also had a negative effect, as a weaker national currency increased the cost of imported goods through exchange rate fluctuations. In addition, the government implemented a large-scale social policy in 2020, introducing social payments to families, businesses, and other social groups. Furthermore, Russia experienced drought conditions in 2020, which led to higher agricultural prices.

However, beginning in 2022, Russia faced a number of serious challenges. After the start of the Special Military Operation in Ukraine, the Russian economy encountered new difficulties in regulating monetary policy.

1) Disconnection of major Russian banks from the SWIFT system. These restrictions worsened trade operations and settlements with foreign partners. As a result, demand increased for alternative financial systems such as the Russian SPFS system and the Chinese CIPS system.

2) Freezing of foreign accounts and gold reserves. Approximately 300 billion USD out of Russia's 640 billion USD in gold and foreign exchange reserves held abroad (in EU countries and the United States) were frozen. These unprecedented decisions caused significant resonance in the global economy. As a consequence, the Central Bank's ability to regulate inflation targeting and stabilize the national currency through foreign exchange interventions became limited.

3) Restrictions on imported goods. Trade embargoes imposed by the EU, the United States, and other countries significantly affected technological development, industrial productivity, and sectors such as aviation, automotive manufacturing, and mechanical engineering. In addition, disruptions in logistics chains and increased delivery times through alternative routes (Turkey, China, and CIS countries) further complicated economic activity.

4) Withdrawal of Western companies from the Russian market. The exit of more than 1,000 foreign subsidiaries from the market resulted in reduced consumer choice and lower competition. Prices for substitute products increased, while the quality of services declined. Import substitution policies also led to higher production costs for domestic analogues.

Figure 3 illustrates the dynamics of the ruble exchange rate against the US dollar. The beginning of the Special Military Operation had a significant impact on the exchange rate in March 2022, which returned by May 2022 to the level observed before this event.

Figure 3. Ruble Devaluation and the Ruble-to-US Dollar Exchange Rate in the Russian Federation in 2022

These factors affected and complicated the implementation of inflation targeting as an instrument of monetary policy in Russia. This led to the depreciation of the ruble, which was especially noticeable in March 2022 (Figure 3). In 2022, due to economic sanctions and restrictions, inflation in Russia reached its peak level of 11.94%. Technical and economic isolation also resulted in the restructuring of Russia's economic relations toward Eastern countries and organizations, including China, the CIS countries, India, the EAEU, and BRICS

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